

SINGULARITY-FREE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: When a layered composite is subjected to an external load it always has stress singularities at certain locations in the composite. Examples are the free-edge where an interface meets a traction-free surface, a sharp notch and a crack. The existence of the singularities is due to the fact that the material is homogeneous in each layer. If the material is inhomogeneous, and if the inhomogeneity is such that the material is cylindrically orthotropic at each location where the singularity would occur if the material were homogeneous, we show that all singularities can be alleviated. In theory therefore a singularity-free composite can be obtained.

KEYWORDS: Anisotropic elasticity, stress singularities, cylindrically uniform, inhomogeneous materials, bimetals, cracks, notches, wedges.

INTRODUCTION

A structural unit that is a composite made of, say, layers of fiber reinforced laminates always have stress singularities at certain locations of the composite. If each layer is assumed to be a *homogeneous* anisotropic elastic material there are stress singularities at the free-edge where an interface between two layers meets a traction-free surface. If the structure is fastened to a rigid wall there are stress singularities at the corner where the composite is attached to the rigid wall. If the structure possesses a notch or a crack there are stress singularities at the notch apex or the crack tip. For a notch or a crack, rounding the notch apex or the crack tip can alleviate the stress singularities. A similar measure can be taken for the corner where the structure meets the rigid wall. However, while the stress singularities can be avoided the *stress intensity factor* may still be too high at these locations depending on the radius of curvature of the rounded corner. As to the free-edge singularities, there is very little that one can do to alleviate the stress singularities.

The situation is much different if each layer is an *inhomogeneous* anisotropic elastic material. A special inhomogeneous material is the *cylindrically*

uniform anisotropic elastic material. A material is *cylindrically uniform* when its stress-strain law referred to a cylindrically coordinate system is the same everywhere. Examples of cylindrically uniform anisotropic materials are tree trunks, carbon fiber [1], certain steel bars, and manufactured composites [2]. In a recent paper [3] a wedge of cylindrically uniform orthotropic elastic materials under anti-plane deformations was studied. The solution depends on one non-dimensional material parameter γ , which is the square root of the ratio of the two shear moduli. For any given wedge angle 2α (no matter how small), one can choose a γ so that the stress at the wedge apex is infinite. In the special case of a crack ($2\alpha=2\pi$) there may be more than one stress singularity at the wedge apex. Some of them can be larger than the square root singularity. On the other hand, one can also choose a γ so that there is no stress singularity at the wedge apex for *any wedge angle*, including the special case of a crack. In the case of plane strain deformations the same remarkable nature prevails [4]. The solution now depends on two non-dimensional materials parameters γ and η . The γ here is the square root of the ratio of two principal elastic stiffnesses. The existence or non-existence of a singularity at the wedge apex depends on both γ and η . If we choose the γ and η properly, there is no stress singularity at the wedge apex for any wedge angle, including the special case of a crack.

The ideas can be extended to a layered composite. We replace the layers by *inhomogeneous* anisotropic elastic materials. At the locations where a stress singularity exists if the layers were homogeneous, the material is locally a *cylindrically uniform orthotropic elastic material*. We will show that one can always choose the material constants in each layer such that there is no stress singularity in the entire composite.

BASIC EQUATIONS FOR CYLINDRICALLY UNIFORM ANISOTROPIC ELASTIC MATERIALS

When an anisotropic elastic material contains a notch or a crack, the stress singularity at the tip of the notch or the crack can be analyzed by studying the stress singularity at the apex of a wedge of wedge angle 2α . In a cylindrically coordinate system (r, θ, x_3) the wedge occupies the region

$$-\alpha \leq \theta \leq \alpha. \quad (1)$$

If we employ the contracted notation

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= \sigma_{rr}, & \sigma_2 &= \sigma_{\theta\theta}, & \sigma_3 &= \sigma_{33}, \\ \sigma_4 &= \sigma_{\theta 3}, & \sigma_5 &= \sigma_{r 3}, & \sigma_6 &= \sigma_{r\theta} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

for the stresses, the equilibrium equations are

$$(r\sigma_1)_{,r} + \sigma_{6,\theta} - \sigma_2 = 0, \quad (r^2\sigma_6)_{,r} + r\sigma_{2,\theta} = 0, \quad (r\sigma_5)_{,r} + \sigma_{4,\theta} = 0, \quad (3)$$

where a subscript comma denotes differentiation. They are satisfied by

$$\sigma_1 = r^{-2}\chi_{,\theta\theta} + r^{-1}\chi_{,r}, \quad \sigma_2 = \chi_{,rr}, \quad \sigma_6 = -(r^{-1}\chi_{,\theta})_{,r}, \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_4 = \psi_{,r}, \quad \sigma_5 = -r^{-1}\psi_{,\theta},$$

in which χ is the Airy stress function [5] for the in-plane stresses and ψ is the stress function for the anti-plane shear stresses. To study the stress singularity at the wedge apex let

$$\chi = A r^{\delta+2} e^{p\theta}, \quad \psi = B r^{\delta+1} e^{p\theta}, \quad (5)$$

where A , B , p , and δ are constants to be determined. Equation (4) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= A(p^2 + \delta + 2)r^\delta e^{p\theta}, & \sigma_2 &= A(\delta + 2)(\delta + 1)r^\delta e^{p\theta}, \\ \sigma_6 &= -A(\delta + 1)pr^\delta e^{p\theta}, & \sigma_4 &= B(\delta + 1)r^\delta e^{p\theta}, & \sigma_5 &= -Bpr^\delta e^{p\theta}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The stresses are singular at $r=0$ when $\delta < 0$ or, if δ is complex, $\text{Re}\delta < 0$.

Let u_r , u_θ , u_3 be the displacements. With the employment of the contracted notation

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_1 &= \varepsilon_{rr}, & \varepsilon_2 &= \varepsilon_{\theta\theta}, & \varepsilon_3 &= \varepsilon_{33}, \\ \varepsilon_4 &= 2\varepsilon_{\theta 3}, & \varepsilon_5 &= 2\varepsilon_{r3}, & \varepsilon_6 &= 2\varepsilon_{r\theta} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

for the strains, the relations between the displacements and strains are

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_1 &= u_{r,r}, & \varepsilon_2 &= r^{-1}(u_{\theta,\theta} + u_r), & \varepsilon_6 &= r^{-1}u_{r,\theta} + r(r^{-1}u_\theta)_{,r}, \\ \varepsilon_5 &= u_{3,r}, & \varepsilon_4 &= r^{-1}u_{3,\theta}, & \varepsilon_3 &= u_{3,3} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The in-plane displacements u_r , u_θ and the anti-plane displacement u_3 are coupled for a general cylindrically anisotropic material. Noticing that $\varepsilon_3 = 0$, the stress-strain law for an anisotropic elastic material can be written as

$$\varepsilon_\alpha = s'_{\alpha\beta} \sigma_\beta, \quad (9)$$

where the $s'_{\alpha\beta}$ are the *reduced* elastic compliances and repeated indices imply summation. $s'_{\alpha\beta}$ are related to the elastic compliances $s_{\alpha\beta}$ by

$$s'_{\alpha\beta} = s_{\alpha\beta} - \frac{s_{\alpha 3} s_{3 \beta}}{s_{33}}. \quad (10)$$

It should be noted that the stress-strain law (9) is referred to a cylindrical coordinate system. Hence the $s'_{\alpha\beta}$ depend on the polar angle θ for a homogeneous material. The $s'_{\alpha\beta}$ are constants when the material is *isotropic* or *cylindrically anisotropic*.

Substitution of σ_β from (6) into (9) gives

$$\varepsilon_\alpha = (A g_\alpha - B h_\alpha) r^\delta e^{p\theta}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$g_\alpha = (p^2 + \delta + 2)s'_{\alpha 1} + (\delta + 2)(\delta + 1)s'_{\alpha 2} - (\delta + 1)ps'_{\alpha 6}, \quad (12)$$

$$h_\alpha = ps'_{\alpha 5} - (\delta + 1)s'_{\alpha 4}.$$

Integration of (8)_{1,3,4} using (11) yields

$$\begin{aligned} u_r &= (\delta + 1)^{-1}(Ag_1 - Bh_1)r^{\delta+1}e^{p\theta}, \\ u_\theta &= \delta^{-1}[(Ag_6 - Bh_6) - p(\delta + 1)^{-1}(Ag_1 - Bh_1)]r^{\delta+1}e^{p\theta} + \omega r, \\ u_3 &= (\delta + 1)^{-1}(Ag_5 - Bh_5)r^{\delta+1}e^{p\theta}, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where ω is an arbitrary constant. The term $u_\theta = \omega r$ represents a rigid-body rotation about the x_3 -axis. It serves a useful purpose for the special case when $\delta=0$ [4]. Insertion of (13) and (11) in the remaining two equations (8)_{2,5} shows that the extra terms that were ignored in obtaining (13) represent a rigid-body displacement, and that (8)_{2,5} are satisfied if

$$\ell_4(p)A = \hat{\ell}_3(p)B, \quad \ell_3(p)A = \ell_2(p)B. \quad (14)$$

In (14),

$$\begin{aligned} \ell_2(p) &= s'_{55}p^2 - 2(\delta + 1)s'_{45}p + (\delta + 1)^2s'_{44}, \\ \ell_3(p) &= s'_{15}p^3 - (\delta + 1)(s'_{14} + s'_{56})p^2 + [(\delta + 1)(\delta + 2)s'_{25} + (\delta + 1)^2s'_{46} \\ &\quad + (\delta + 2)s'_{15}]p - (\delta + 1)(\delta + 2)[s'_{14} + (\delta + 1)s'_{24}], \\ \hat{\ell}_3(p) &= s'_{15}p^3 - (\delta + 1)(s'_{14} + s'_{56})p^2 + [\delta(\delta + 1)s'_{25} + (\delta + 1)^2s'_{46} \\ &\quad - \delta s'_{15}]p + \delta(\delta + 1)[s'_{14} - (\delta + 1)s'_{24}], \\ \ell_4(p) &= s'_{11}p^4 - 2(\delta + 1)s'_{16}p^3 + [(\delta + 1)^2(s'_{66} + 2s'_{12}) + 2s'_{11}]p^2 \\ &\quad - 2(\delta + 1)[(\delta + 1)^2s'_{26} + s'_{16}]p + \delta(\delta + 2)[(\delta + 1)^2s'_{22} - s'_{11}]. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Here ℓ_2 is a polynomial in p of degree two, ℓ_3 and $\hat{\ell}_3$ are polynomials in p of degree three and ℓ_4 is a polynomial in p of degree four. Equation (14) has a non-trivial solution for A and B if

$$\ell_2(p)\ell_4(p) - \ell_3(p)\hat{\ell}_3(p) = 0. \quad (16)$$

This is a sextic algebraic equation in p . It is similar to the Lekhnitskii [5] formalism for a two-dimensional deformation of a homogeneous anisotropic elastic material. The p here, however, need not be all complex for a real δ .

The sextic equation (16) provides six roots for p . The general solution for the stresses and displacements is obtained by superimposing six solutions of the form (13) and (6) associated with the six p .

CYLINDRICALLY ORTHOTROPIC MATERIALS

When the material is cylindrically orthotropic with its symmetry planes coinciding with the cylindrical coordinate planes, the h_1 , h_6 and g_5 defined in

(12) vanish. Using (12) for orthotropic materials, (13) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} u_r &= Ar^{\delta+1}e^{p\theta}[(\delta+1)^{-1}(p^2 + \delta + 2)s'_{11} + (\delta+2)s'_{12}], \\ u_\theta &= -Ar^{\delta+1}e^{p\theta}p\delta^{-1}[(\delta+1)^{-1}(p^2 + \delta + 2)s'_{11} + (\delta+2)s'_{12} + (\delta+1)s'_{66}] + \omega r, \\ u_3 &= -Br^{\delta+1}e^{p\theta}p(\delta+1)^{-1}s'_{55}. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The arbitrary constant B is associated with the anti-plane displacement u_3 while the constant A is associated with the in-plane displacement (u_r, u_θ) . Hence u_3 and (u_r, u_θ) are uncoupled. The coefficients of the cubic polynomials ℓ_3 and ℓ_3 shown in (15) vanish and (16) reduces to

$$\ell_2(p) = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \ell_4(p) = 0. \quad (18)$$

Equations (18)_{1,2} apply, respectively, to anti-plane and in-plane deformations.

Anti-plane Deformation

Equation (18)₁ for cylindrically orthotropic elastic material is

$$s'_{55}p^2 + (\delta+1)^2s'_{44} = 0 \quad (19)$$

from which we obtain

$$p = \pm(\delta+1)i\gamma, \quad \gamma = \sqrt{s'_{44}/s'_{55}} = \sqrt{\mu_{r3}/\mu_{\theta3}}. \quad (20)$$

γ is the square root of the ratio of the two shear moduli μ_{r3} and $\mu_{\theta3}$. Since both shear moduli are positive and nonzero, γ can be any positive and nonzero number. The nonzero stresses σ_4 and σ_5 obtained from (6) and the displacement u_3 obtained from (17) by superposing two solutions associated with the two p shown in (20) are

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_4 &= r^\delta \{-a \sin(\delta+1)\gamma\theta + b \cos(\delta+1)\gamma\theta\}, \\ \sigma_5 &= \gamma r^\delta \{a \cos(\delta+1)\gamma\theta + b \sin(\delta+1)\gamma\theta\}, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

$$u_3 = \gamma s'_{55}(\delta+1)^{-1}r^{\delta+1} \{a \cos(\delta+1)\gamma\theta + b \sin(\delta+1)\gamma\theta\},$$

where a and b are arbitrary constants. The stresses at $r=0$ are singular when

$$-1 < \text{Re}\delta < 0. \quad (22)$$

The inequality on the left insures that the strain energy at the wedge apex is bounded. Thus we will be interested in δ whose real part is between zero and -1 .

When the sides $\theta=\pm\alpha$ are traction-free the boundary conditions are

$$\sigma_4=0 \quad \text{at} \quad \theta=\pm\alpha. \quad (23)$$

Imposition of (23) on (21)₁ leads to

$$\begin{aligned}
-a \sin(\delta + 1)\gamma\alpha + b \cos(\delta + 1)\gamma\alpha &= 0, \\
a \sin(\delta + 1)\gamma\alpha + b \cos(\delta + 1)\gamma\alpha &= 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

The two equations are compatible if

$$\sin 2(\delta + 1)\gamma\alpha = 0,$$

or

$$2(\delta + 1)\gamma\alpha = k\pi, \quad (k=1,2,\dots). \tag{25}$$

Equation (25) gives

$$\delta = \frac{k\pi}{2\gamma\alpha} - 1, \quad (k=1,2,\dots). \tag{26}$$

Whether the stress at the wedge apex is singular or not depends on whether $\delta < 0$ or $\delta > 0$. If

$$\gamma > k\pi / 2\alpha, \quad (k=1,2,\dots), \tag{27}$$

$\delta < 0$ for at least one integer k . One can always choose a γ so that (27) holds. Thus *the stress at the wedge apex can be singular for any wedge angle*. For the special case of a crack, $2\alpha = 2\pi$ so that (27) is satisfied by $\gamma > 1/2$. If we choose $\gamma = 3$, the δ of (27) for $k=1,2,\dots,5$ are

$$\delta = -\frac{5}{6}, \quad -\frac{4}{6}, \quad -\frac{3}{6}, \quad -\frac{2}{6}, \quad -\frac{1}{6}. \tag{28}$$

The first two are stronger than the square root singularity.

There is no stress singularity at the wedge apex if $\delta > 0$ or, by (26),

$$\gamma < \pi / 2\alpha. \tag{29}$$

Since $2\alpha \leq 2\pi$, (29) is satisfied for all wedge angles if $\gamma < 1/2$. Thus when $\gamma < 1/2$, there is no stress singularity at the wedge apex for any wedge angle, including the special case of a crack.

In-Plane Deformation

Equation (18)₂ for cylindrically orthotropic elastic material is

$$s'_{11}p^4 + [(\delta + 1)^2(s'_{66} + 2s'_{12}) + 2s'_{11}]p^2 + \delta(\delta + 2)[(\delta + 1)^2s'_{22} - s'_{11}] = 0. \tag{30}$$

The 5×5 matrix $s'_{\alpha\beta}$, after deleting the third row and the third column that contain only zero elements, is symmetric and positive definite if the strain energy is positive [6,7]. Hence the $s'_{\alpha\beta}$ appearing in (30) must satisfy the conditions

$$s'_{11} > 0, \quad s'_{11}s'_{22} - s'_{12}^2 > 0, \quad s'_{66} > 0. \tag{31}$$

Equations (31)_{1,2} imply that $s'_{22} > 0$. If (31)₂ is written as

$$(\sqrt{s'_{11}s'_{22}} + s'_{12})(\sqrt{s'_{11}s'_{22}} - s'_{12}) > 0,$$

it is easily concluded that

$$\sqrt{s'_{11}s'_{22}} \pm s'_{12} > 0. \quad (32)$$

Equation (30) can be rewritten as

$$p^4 + 2Up^2 + V = 0 \quad (33)$$

in which

$$U = (\delta + 1)^2 \eta + 1, \quad V = \delta(\delta + 2)[(\delta + 1)^2 \gamma^2 - 1], \quad (34)$$

and

$$\eta = \frac{s'_{66} + 2s'_{12}}{2s'_{11}}, \quad \gamma = \sqrt{s'_{22}/s'_{11}} = \sqrt{C_{11}/C_{22}}. \quad (35)$$

The $C_{\alpha\beta}$ are the elastic stiffnesses. The four roots of (33) are

$$p_1 = i\lambda_1, \quad p_2 = i\lambda_2, \quad p_3 = -i\lambda_1, \quad p_4 = -i\lambda_2, \quad (36)$$

where

$$\lambda_1 = \sqrt{U + \sqrt{W}}, \quad \lambda_2 = \sqrt{U - \sqrt{W}}, \quad (37)$$

and

$$W = U^2 - V = (\delta + 1)^2 \{ \delta(\delta + 2)(\eta^2 - \gamma^2) + (\eta + 1)^2 \}. \quad (38)$$

They depend on the two non-dimensional material parameters γ and η . In terms of γ and η , (32) can be written as

$$\gamma \pm (\eta - \varepsilon) > 0, \quad \varepsilon = \frac{s'_{66}}{2s'_{11}} > 0. \quad (39)$$

Since ε can be any positive number, we must consider γ and η in the region

$$\gamma > 0, \quad -\gamma < \eta < \infty. \quad (40)$$

In the special case of cylindrically cubic materials, $\gamma=1$ so that

$$(\lambda_1 \pm \lambda_2)^2 = 2[(\delta + 1)^2 \eta + 1 \pm \delta(\delta + 2)].$$

For an isotropic material, $\gamma=\eta=1$ and we have

$$\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 2(\delta + 1), \quad \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 = 2,$$

or

$$\lambda_1 = \delta + 2, \quad \lambda_2 = \delta. \quad (41)$$

The four p are distinct. For a wedge of cylindrically anisotropic elastic material, there is no degeneracy when the material becomes isotropic.

With the four p given in (36) the general solution for the stresses is obtained by superposing four solutions of the form shown in (6). The non-zero stresses can be written in real form as

$$\sigma_1 = (\delta + 1)^{-1} r^\delta \{ (\delta + 2 - \lambda_1^2) (a_1 \cos \lambda_1 \theta + b_1 \sin \lambda_1 \theta) \}$$

$$+(\delta + 2 - \lambda_2^2)(a_2 \cos \lambda_2 \theta + b_2 \sin \lambda_2 \theta)\}, \quad (42)$$

$$\sigma_2 = (\delta + 2)r^\delta \{a_1 \cos \lambda_1 \theta + b_1 \sin \lambda_1 \theta + a_2 \cos \lambda_2 \theta + b_2 \sin \lambda_2 \theta\},$$

$$\sigma_6 = r^\delta \{a_1 \lambda_1 \sin \lambda_1 \theta - b_1 \lambda_1 \cos \lambda_1 \theta + a_2 \lambda_2 \sin \lambda_2 \theta - b_2 \lambda_2 \cos \lambda_2 \theta\}.$$

where a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 are arbitrary constants.

Again, we consider a wedge of wedge angle 2α that occupies the region

$$-\alpha \leq \theta \leq \alpha. \quad (43)$$

The deformations associated with a_1 and a_2 shown in (42) are *symmetric* with $\theta=0$ while the deformations associated with b_1 and b_2 are *skew-symmetric* with $\theta=0$. Since any deformation can be decomposed into one that is symmetric with $\theta=0$ and one that is skew-symmetric with $\theta=0$, we can study symmetric and skew-symmetric deformations separately. If the sides $\theta=\pm\alpha$ of the wedge are traction-free, we have

$$\sigma_2 = \sigma_6 = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad \theta = \pm\alpha. \quad (44)$$

For the *symmetric* deformation, insertion of (42) into (44) leads to

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 \cos \lambda_1 \alpha + a_2 \cos \lambda_2 \alpha &= 0, \\ a_1 \lambda_1 \sin \lambda_1 \alpha + a_2 \lambda_2 \sin \lambda_2 \alpha &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

A non-trivial solution for a_1, a_2 exists if

$$\lambda_1 \sin \lambda_1 \alpha \cos \lambda_2 \alpha - \lambda_2 \cos \lambda_1 \alpha \sin \lambda_2 \alpha = 0, \quad (46a)$$

or

$$(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \sin(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2) \alpha + (\lambda_1 - \lambda_2) \sin(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \alpha = 0. \quad (46b)$$

Depending on the values of γ and η , the order of the stress singularity δ can be real or complex. We are interested in the real part of δ that is between -1 and zero. A semi-analytical investigation of all roots δ of (46) showed that there is no singularity for any wedge angle 2α if [4]

$$\begin{aligned} -\gamma < \eta < -1/2, \quad \gamma \leq \gamma_*, \\ 3\gamma_*^2 &= (2\eta + 1)^2 + 2. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

For the *skew-symmetric* deformation a similar analysis lead to

$$\sin \lambda_1 \alpha \cos \lambda_2 \alpha - \lambda_1 \cos \lambda_1 \alpha (\sin \lambda_2 \alpha) \lambda_2^{-1} = 0 \quad (48a)$$

or

$$\{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \sin(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2) \alpha - (\lambda_1 - \lambda_2) \sin(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \alpha\} \lambda_2^{-1} = 0. \quad (48b)$$

A semi-analytical investigation of all roots δ of (48) showed that there is no singularity for any wedge angle 2α if [4]

$$-\gamma < \eta < 0.02288, \quad \gamma \leq \hat{\gamma}_*, \quad (49)$$

$$5\hat{\gamma}_*^2 = 3(2\eta + 1)^2 + 2.$$

Free-Edge Stresses

Let $\theta=0$ be the interface between two cylindrically orthotropic elastic materials. Material 1 occupies the region $0 \leq \theta \leq \pi/2$ while material 2 occupies the region $-\pi/2 \leq \theta \leq 0$. For simplicity we consider the anti-plane deformation. The stresses σ_4 , σ_5 and the displacement u_3 for material 1 are given by (21) while σ_4 , σ_5 and u_3 for material 2 will be written as

$$\sigma_4 = r^\delta \left\{ -\hat{a} \sin(\delta + 1)\hat{\gamma}\theta + \hat{b} \cos(\delta + 1)\hat{\gamma}\theta \right\},$$

$$\sigma_5 = \hat{\gamma} r^\delta \left\{ \hat{a} \cos(\delta + 1)\hat{\gamma}\theta + \hat{b} \sin(\delta + 1)\hat{\gamma}\theta \right\}, \quad (50)$$

$$u_3 = \hat{\gamma} \hat{s}'_{55} (\delta + 1)^{-1} r^{\delta+1} \left\{ \hat{a} \cos(\delta + 1)\hat{\gamma}\theta + \hat{b} \sin(\delta + 1)\hat{\gamma}\theta \right\},$$

where \hat{a} , \hat{b} , $\hat{\gamma}$ and \hat{s}'_{55} are constants referred to material 2. The continuity at the interface $\theta=0$ demands that σ_4 and u_3 in (21) and (50) are identical at $\theta=0$, i.e.,

$$b = \hat{b}, \quad \gamma \hat{s}'_{55} a = \hat{\gamma} \hat{s}'_{55} \hat{a}. \quad (51)$$

The vanishing of σ_4 at $\theta=\pi/2$ and $\theta=-\pi/2$ leads to

$$-a \sin \kappa + b \cos \kappa = 0, \quad (52)$$

$$\hat{a} \sin \hat{\kappa} + \hat{b} \cos \hat{\kappa} = 0$$

where

$$\kappa = (\delta + 1)\gamma\pi/2, \quad \hat{\kappa} = (\delta + 1)\hat{\gamma}\pi/2. \quad (53)$$

It is readily shown that (51) and (52) have a nontrivial solution for a , b , \hat{a} , \hat{b} if

$$\frac{\tan \kappa}{s'_{55} \kappa} + \frac{\tan \hat{\kappa}}{\hat{s}'_{55} \hat{\kappa}} = 0. \quad (54)$$

Since there are arbitrary constants s'_{55} , \hat{s}'_{55} , γ and $\hat{\gamma}$ in (54) it is not difficult to choose these constants such that (54) is satisfied only for $\text{Re}(\delta) > 0$. We then have no stress singularity at the free-edge.

The analysis for the in-plane deformation is similar, except that it is algebraically more complicated. We will have more constants to choose for the bimetals. It is even easier to choose the constants so that there is no stress singularity at the free-edge when the deformation is in-plane.

We have shown that, if we introduce a cylindrically orthotropic elastic material at each location in a layered composite (such as at a notch, crack, or free-edge), the existence of a stress singularity can be completely alleviated. It is hoped that the technology in the future will be able to manufacture an *inhomogeneous* laminate with specified values of γ and η at each location where a stress singularity would otherwise occur if the laminate were homogeneous. We would then have a singularity-free composite.

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